

Orthomolecular Somatic and Psychiatric Medicine

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I greatly appreciate the honor of being associated with the International Society for Research on Vital Substances, Nutrition, and the Diseases of Civilization, in succession to my friend Dr. Albert Schweitzer, and I take this opportunity to express my thanks to the members and officers of the Society.

Also, I express my regret that it has not been possible for me to be present at the Thirteenth International Convention of the Society. Some difficult problems associated with my move to La Jolla and the assumption of my Professorship in the University of California made it necessary for me to abandon my tentative plan of coming to Luxembourg to participate in the Convention.

In this communication to the Society I present some thoughts about molecular medicine, and especially about the use in the treatment of both physical and mental disease of substances that are normally present in the human body and are required for life.

I have introduced the expression orthomolecular medicine to describe one aspect of molecular medicine. In 1949 my co-workers Harvey Itano, S. J. Singer, and Ibert C. Wells and I published a paper with the title Sickle-cell Anemia, A Molecular Disease. In this paper we communicated our discovery that patients with the disease sickle-cell anemia have in their erythrocytes a form of hemoglobin differing from that manufactured by other people. We pointed out that the difference in molecular structure of the hemoglobin manufactured by persons suffering from this disease leads to a difference in properties of the hemoglobin molecules from those manufactured by other people, and that this difference in properties is responsible for the manifestations of the disease. The disease can properly be described as a disease of the hemoglobin molecule, rather than of the erythrocyte itself, and in consequence it may be called a molecular disease.

Later work in our laboratories in the California Institute of Technology and by other investigators elsewhere showed that the hemoglobin molecule contains four polypeptide chains, two of one kind, the alpha chains, and two of another kind, the beta chains, and also that sickle-cell anemia hemoglobin differs from normal hemoglobin in having one of the 146 amino-acid residues in each beta chain different from that in normal human hemoglobin, the difference being a replacement of a glutamic-acid residue in the sixth position from the amino end of the beta chain in normal adult human hemoglobin by a residue of valine.

Many other abnormal forms of human hemoglobin have now been discovered, and many diseases have been recognized as diseases of the hemoglobin molecule. Other molecular diseases have also been identified. These diseases for the most part are genetic diseases, the result of a gene mutation.

The disease phenylketonuria, discovered about forty years ago by Følling in Norway, may be considered a molecular disease. This disease involves a gene mutation such that the patient fails to manufacture molecules of an enzyme normally present in the liver, which catalyzes the oxidation of phenylalanine to tyrosine, or produces an abnormal enzyme, with greatly reduced catalytic activity. The patients are homozygotes, who have inherited the

gene in double dose, usually from a heterozygotic father and a heterozygotic mother. The patients on a normal diet have in their tissues abnormally high concentrations of phenylalanine and some of its reaction products, which cause the physical and the mental manifestations of the disease, severe eczema, mental deficiency, and so on. The treatment that has considerable success is to place the patients, from the age of one month or two months, on a diet of foods from which a considerable amount of phenylalanine has been removed. This decrease in the amount of phenylalanine ingested by the patients results in an approximation to the normal or optimal concentrations of phenylalanine and its reaction products in the body fluids, and to the alleviation of the physical and mental manifestations of the disease.

Another molecular disease for which a molecular treatment is available is diabetes. This disease results from a gene abnormality such that the patient does not manufacture the proper amount of the hormone insulin. The disease can be controlled by the injection of insulin, to bring the concentration to approximately the normal or optimal value.

Phenylketonuria involves the presence in the body of phenylalanine and its reaction products in amounts greater than normal. It is treated by reducing the intake of phenylalanine and in this way reducing the concentration of this substance and its reaction products to approximately the normal level. Diabetes involves a deficiency of insulin. It is treated by injecting insulin, and increasing the concentration to approximately the normal value. I have reached the conclusion, through arguments summarized in the following paragraphs, that a general method of treatment of disease, which may be called orthomolecular therapy, may be found to be of great value, and may turn out often to be the best method of treatment for many patients.

Orthomolecular therapy is the treatment of disease by the provision of the optimal molecular constitution of the body, especially the optimal concentration of substances that are normally present in the human body and are required for life. The adjective orthomolecular is used to express the idea of the right molecules in the right concentration. This word may be criticized as a Greek-Latin hybrid, but I have not thought of a better word.

I believe that orthomolecular therapy may have a special value in the treatment of mental disease. The functioning of the mind is dependent on its molecular environment, the molecular structure of the brain. The presence in the brain of molecules N,N-diethyl-D-lysergamide, mescaline, or some other schizophrenogenic substance often is associated with profound psychotic effects. The phenomenon of general anesthesia also illustrates the dependence of the mind (consciousness, ephemeral memory) on its molecular environment.

The proper functioning of the mind is known to require the presence in the brain of molecules of many different substances. For example, mental disease, usually associated also with physical disease, results from a low concentration in the brain of thiamine (Vitamin B₁), nicotinic acid or nicotinamide (B₃), pyridoxine (B₆), cyanocobalamin (B₁₂), biotin (H), and ascorbic acid (Vitamin C).

Also, there is evidence that mental function and behavior are affected by changes in the concentration in the brain of any one of a number of other substances that are normally present, such as glutamic acid, uric acid, and gamma-aminobutyric acid.

Optimal Molecular Concentrations

Several arguments may be advanced in support of the thesis that the optimal molecular concentrations of substances normally present in the body may be different from the concentrations provided by the diet and by the gene-controlled synthetic mechanisms of the body, and also, for essential nutrilites, such as vitamins, essential amino acids, and essential fatty acids, different from the minimal daily amounts required for life for the average human being or the "recommended" daily amounts suggested for good health.

One argument can be developed through consideration of the process of evolution and natural selection. The process of evolution does not necessarily result in the normal provision of optimal molecular concentrations. Let us use ascorbic acid as an example. Dr. Irwin Stone has pointed out that of the mammals that have been studied in respect to their need for ascorbic acid, the only species that have lost the power to synthesize this substance and that accordingly require it in the diet are man, other primates (Rhesus monkey, Formosan long-tail monkey, ring-tail or brown Capuchin monkey), the guinea pig, and an Indian fruit-eating bat (*Pteropus medius*); in addition one bird, the Red-vented Bulbul (*Pycnonotus Cafer*) is unable to synthesize its own ascorbic acid. Presumably the loss of the gene or genes controlling the synthesis of the enzyme or enzymes involved in the conversion of glucose to ascorbic acid occurred some twenty million years ago in the common ancestor of man and other primates, and occurred independently for the guinea pig and other isolated species mentioned above, in each case in an environment such that ascorbic acid was provided by the available food. The advantage to the mutant of being rid of the machinery for the synthesis of ascorbic acid (decrease in cell size and energy requirement, liberation of machinery for other purposes) might well be large. A disadvantage nearly as large resulting from a less than optimal supply of dietary ascorbic acid would not prevent the replacement of the earlier species by the mutant. Hence the amount of the vitamin provided by the diet available at the time of the mutation might be less than the optimal amount. Moreover, it is possible that the environment has changed during the last twenty million years in such a way as to provide a decreased amount of the vitamin for the average human being. Even a serious disadvantage of the changed environment would not lead to a mutation restoring the synthetic mechanism, because of the small probability of such mutations, far smaller than of those resulting in loss of function.

Individual Variation

The human race is characterized by large genetic heterogeneity. Enzyme concentrations in the tissues of different persons often differ by the factor of two or even a factor of ten or one hundred, as has been pointed out especially by Professor Roger J. Williams of the University of Texas. Heterozygosity in the gene for phenylketonuria halves the amount of the enzyme phenylalanine hydroxylase, and homozygosity in this gene reduces the amount or effectiveness of the enzyme by two or more orders of magnitude.

Molecular Concentrations and Rate of Reactions

The rate of an enzyme-catalysed reaction is approximately proportional to the concentration of reactant until concentrations are reached that largely saturate the enzyme. The saturating concentration is larger for a defective enzyme with decreased combining power for the substrate than for the normal enzyme. For such a defective enzyme the catalysed reaction could be made to take place at or near its normal rate by an increase in the concentration

of the substrate. Moreover, an increase in concentration of an enzyme inhibitor can decrease the rate of reaction; for example, an increase in concentration of nicotinamide, with the consequent inhibition of the enzyme diphosphopyridine nucleotidase, decreases the rate of hydrolysis of diphosphopyridine nucleotide.

Evidence from Microbiological Genetics

Many mutant microorganisms are known to require, as a supplement to the medium on which they are grown, a substance that is synthesized by the corresponding wild-type organism. An example is the "pyridoxineless" mutant of *Neurospora Sitophila* reported by G. W. Beadle and E. L. Tatum in their first *Neurospora* paper, published in the Proceedings of the United States National Academy of Sciences in 1941. They found the rate of growth of this mutant on their standard medium to be only nine per cent of that of the wild type. When pyridoxine (Vitamin B₆) is added to the medium, the rate of growth at first increases nearly linearly with the concentration of the added pyridoxine, and then the growth-rate curve bends rather sharply, and continues to increase with a much smaller slope. The region of concentrations in which the growth increases rapidly with increase in concentration may be considered to be the region of vitamin deficiency, and the concentration at which the curve changes to much smaller slope may be considered to correspond to an "adequate" or "recommended" amount of the vitamin, in that the growth rate of the mutant is then only a few per cent less than that of the wild strain, and the amount of the vitamin would have to be increased three-fold to make up the difference.

Increasing the concentration of the growth substance to thirty-five times the adequate concentration for the mutant causes an increase in growth rate by about twenty-five per cent. The growth rate of the mutant is then ten per cent greater than that of the wild type. An increase in growth rate or in some other function of magnitude twenty-five per cent or ten per cent might under some circumstances be of great value, and might mean the difference between life and death or between good health and poor health, either physical or mental. Especially if the growth substance is non-toxic and free from side reactions, its therapeutic use in large amounts might well be justified. Ascorbic acid, for example, is non-toxic for all or almost all human beings. It is required for life in amounts of a few milligrams per day. The ingestion of large amounts, three or five grams per day, seems to improve the general health of human beings, and to provide greater resistance to colds and other infectious diseases. I believe that it is likely that the optimal intake of ascorbic acid is far greater than the "approved" or "recommended" intake, and that a significant improvement in the health of human beings could be achieved by approximating this optimal intake.

Orthomolecular Psychiatry

The functioning of the brain is more sensitively dependent on the rate of chemical reaction than the functioning of other organs and tissues. I believe that mental disease is for the most part caused by abnormal molecular concentrations of essential substances. The operation of chance in the selection, for the child, of half of the complement of genes of the father and mother leads to bad as well as to good genotypes, and the selection of foods (and drugs) in a world that is undergoing rapid scientific and technological change may often be far from the best. Significant improvement in the mental health of many persons, especially those with borderline or mild mental illness or mental retardation, might be achieved by the provision of the optimal molecular concentrations of substances normally present in the human body, especially those that are not toxic or have low toxicity.

Among these substances, the essential nutrilites may be the most worthy of extensive research and more thorough clinical trial than they have yet received.

L(+)-Glutamic acid is a non-essential amino acid that is present at rather high concentration in brain and nerve tissue, and plays an essential role in the functioning of

this tissue. It is normally ingested (in protein) in amounts of five to ten grams per day. It is not toxic; large doses may cause increased motor activity and nausea. In 1944 Price, Waelsch, and Putnam (Journal of the American Medical Association) reported favorable results for glutamic acid treatment of convulsive disorders (benefit to one out of three or four patients with petit mal epilepsy). Many investigators then studied the effects of glutamic acid on the intelligence and behavior of persons with different degrees and kinds of mental retardation. Increase in intelligence and improvement in personality have been reported for many patients with mild or moderate mental deficiency, when given doses of ten grams to twenty grams per day of L(+)-glutamic acid, adjusted to the patient as the amount somewhat less than required to cause hyperactivity.

Nicotinic acid, when its use was introduced, cured hundreds of thousands of pellagra patients of their psychoses, as well as of the physical manifestations of their disease. For this purpose only small doses are required; the recommended daily allowance (U.S. National Research Council) is twelve milligrams per day. In 1940 Streitwieser and his associates reported some success in the treatment of severe depression and other forms of mental disease by use of large doses of nicotinic acid, three grams or more per day. Other investigators, especially A. Hoffer of Saskatchewan and H. Osmond of New York, have advocated and used nicotinic acid in large doses for the treatment of schizophrenia. The dosage recommended by Hoffer is three grams per day, or more, up to eighteen grams per day, as determined by the response of the patient, of either nicotinic acid or nicotinamide, together with three grams per day of ascorbic acid. Nicotinic acid and nicotinamide are non-toxic (LD 50 not known for humans, but probably over 200 grams), and their side effects, even in continued massive doses, seem not to be commonly serious. The advantages of nicotinic acid therapy have been summarized by Osmond and Hoffer (The Lancet 10 Feb. 1962, 316) in the following words: "Niacin (nicotinic acid) has some though not all the qualities of an ideal treatment: it is safe, cheap (less than one cent per gram), and easy to administer, and it uses a known pharmaceutical substance which can be taken for years on end if necessary ... it does not seem to affect the more chronic illnesses, and even in acute illnesses its action is often less dramatic than that of some of the phenothiazines. Its protective qualities, continuing long after patients have stopped taking it, are puzzling ... it has been proved to reduce the level of cholesterol in the blood. It seems to benefit some deliria not obviously associated with vitamin lack, and is claimed to improve many cases of intractable

rheumatism. In our view it is a useful adjunct in the treatment of schizophrenia, both for acute cases and to reduce the chance of relapses."

It is my opinion, for reasons presented in the opening arguments of this paper, that for those patients for whom it is effective the control of mental disease by varying the concentrations in the brain of non-toxic substances that are normally present, such as nicotinic acid and ascorbic acid, is to be preferred to the use of phenylthiazines and other means of therapy that involve a greater insult to the body and mind.

Varying the intake of other vitamins has also been used to some extent in psychiatry. The mental deterioration accompanying aging and cerebral vascular disease may be alleviated by supplementary biflavonoids (Vitamin P) and ascorbic acid. The use of cyanocobalamin (B₁₂) in the treatment of mental disease has been reported, as well as the use of pyridoxine (B₆).

I believe that the study of the functioning of the brain in its relation to the concentrations and intake of the vitamins, essential amino acids, and other substances normally present in the brain constitutes a field of research in which much more work needs to be done. Biochemical and genetic arguments support the idea that orthomolecular therapy, the provision for the individual human being of the optimal concentrations of important normal constituents of the human body, may be the preferred treatment for many patients, especially those with mild mental retardation or mild psychosis. I suggest that this therapy, to be successful, should involve the thorough study of the individual, and continued attention to him, such as is customary in psychoanalysis but not in conventional chemotherapy. There is the possibility that analysis of body fluids and tests of the ability of the individual to utilize essential substances may indicate the types of orthomolecular therapy that would be most likely to be effective for the patient.

I express the hope that the members of the Society and other medical investigators will find the foregoing discussion of orthomolecular medicine interesting and suggestive, and that added attention will be given in the future to the possibility of improving the mental and physical health of human beings by varying the concentrations of substances normally present in the human body.

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